

USE OF ROLE-PLAY AND DIDACTIC GAME IN EFL CLASSROOMS TO IMPROVE STUDENTS SPEAKING SKILLS

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Abstract: Role-playing and lexical games in foreign language classes are considered in the context of modern pedagogical concepts of edutainment and gamification. The game methodology for introducing content and procedural entertainment elements into the educational process is used as a didactic tool for mastering professionally oriented video materials when studying English at university.

Keywords: edutainment, role-playing and vocabulary games, gamification, university, video materials, electronic resources.

INTRODUCTION

Due to the development of information and communication technologies, the use of video materials in teaching foreign languages at a university has become so widespread that almost no teacher can do without this resource. It should be noted that video materials are now widely used not only in the classroom, but also in the extracurricular independent work of students, who can download the video using the link provided by the teacher or receive the video by e-mail. It is well known that independent work with video materials increases students' interest in a foreign language, their motivation, but for better mastery of video content, the teacher needs to think over the methodology of classroom work with the lexical content of the video.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It seems to us that a possible option for classroom work on mastering the content of video materials is the use of video-related role-playing and lexical games. This is organically present in modern methods of teaching a foreign language in the popular edutainment technology using entertainment elements to increase the motivation of students. This term combines two seemingly opposite concepts: entertainment and learning. The concepts of learning through entertainment are especially relevant when teaching students aged 18-22. This is due to the fact that, unlike the older generation, modern students prefer alternative ways of obtaining information. The constant use of computer technology affects their cognitive skills. The relevance of the study of edutainment technology in teaching foreign languages is due to the fact that this direction is new, developing, requiring the development of methods for introducing entertainment elements into the educational process. The term edutainment is, in our opinion, broader than the equally popular term gamification, which implies the widespread use of games in the educational process, the coordination of game goals

and educational process goals, and the development of methods for testing the effectiveness of the implemented gamification system. However, such a system in itself does not lead to the formation of sustainable motivation and involvement in the educational, work, or business process. Successful implementation of a gamification system is often accidental, when developers intuitively found an approach to the target audience and caused the formation of the behavior they need.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After the students have watched the first video, which provides introductory information about the American company CISCO, which develops and sells network equipment intended mainly for large organizations and telecommunications enterprises, the students are asked to take part in a role-playing game Getting a job at CISCO.

Role-playing game. First, the director of the company and four candidates for the available vacancy of a sales representative of the company are selected for the game. Four candidates apply for this position, each of whom has their own negative and positive qualities. In turn, each candidate has two or three representatives for support from a group of students. The task of the representative of the candidate for a position at CISCO is to convince the other participants in the discussion and the director of the company that it is his candidate who has all the necessary skills and personal qualities for this position.

At the same time, the other participants in the game must find as many shortcomings as possible in this candidate and convince the director of the company that this candidate will not contribute to the development and prosperity of the company, and their candidates for the same position will be able to make a great contribution. After the debate is over, the director decides whether to hire the candidate. The director must give his logically sound decision. It should be noted that all students from each support group receive an additional point if they managed to convince their opponents of their rightness. Below is Table 1, which indicates the main characteristics and skills that candidates for the position of sales representative at CISCO must have, and the attractive working conditions at the company. The characteristic features of four candidates applying for this position are presented in Table 2.

Table 1. Required characteristics of candidates for the position and the company's guarantees for working conditions

Position	CISCO Sales Representative for work in the regions of Uzbekistan
Required Skills and Experience	Enthusiasm, social competence, fluency in English, higher education, more than three years of experience in CISCO, necessary computer skills, driver's license
Salary and Benefits	Decent salary, four weeks paid vacation, free meals, growth potential in a prestigious company

Table 2. Personal characteristics of the four candidates

Mark Age 56	Kate Age 30	Jerry Age 20	Susan Age 45. Has two children
Has been in this position for 15 years	Has been working in public relations for 8 years	Never heard of this company	Technical education
He had a nervous breakdown two years ago	Hot-tempered	Able to work under pressure	She needs a flexible work schedule
He has a tendency to argue with people in authority. Ambitious, creative, decisive.	Overly ambitious, conscientious, stubborn, energetic, polite	Proactive, confident, sociable, reliable, arrogant	A perfectionist who tries not to leave things unfinished.
Procrastinates until the last minute	Computer skills. Driver's license	Computer skills. No driver's license	Withdrawn, bossy, responsible, decisive

The selection of students for the roles of the candidates listed in the table, who were supposed to emphasize only their positive qualities when presenting themselves for the position, turned out to be quite successful, and three of the four candidates advertised themselves briskly, while the fourth candidate, due to his insufficient language competence, behaved very modestly. The members of the conditional "personnel committee" appointed by the teacher practiced asking "tricky" questions that emphasized the negative qualities of the candidates. The students were so carried away by the game that they sometimes even interrupted each other, trying to ask the right question. The choice of a worthy candidate was decided by a general secret vote, and, ironically, it turned out to be the same modest candidate who received the award token. This role-playing game performs an expressed communicative function; students interact with each other, discussing the personal qualities of candidates for the existing vacancy. Role-playing games have a frontal-group character, and they develop students' oral skills to a greater extent than subsequent lexical games. Role-playing games are an excellent way to make students practice using a foreign language. Games "simulate real-life situations and provide students with the opportunity to act as they would in a real situation" [2].

Lexical games. Pictures, descriptions of situations, instructions, technical means, and texts of literary works are widely used to create situations for the purpose of mastering new vocabulary. However, there are also a large number of games, the use

of which in class will make the process of mastering new vocabulary an exciting activity. Most researchers [3] consider it appropriate to conduct a game at the final stage of working with vocabulary on a topic, since the game provides an opportunity to use new material in a communication situation. Although games can be used at any stage of working on foreign-language vocabulary, for our methodology we considered the final stage of mastering video content to be the most suitable. For example, the lexical game with cards for the second video was devoted to mastering three key words on the topic of the video: hub, switch, and router. The students, divided into three groups, were given three sets of cards with translations, the first of which contained all the functions of the specified components, the second presented all the advantages of these components, and the third set contained only their disadvantages. The first group of students represented the interests of the Hub and had to choose the cards related to the Hub from the three sets as quickly as possible. The second group was responsible for describing the switch, and the third group for describing the router, and they also had to choose the corresponding cards from the three sets as quickly as possible. In the end, the Hub team won, although they were reprimanded for being too active and appropriating someone else's advantages. The lexical game based on the third video clip is a creative task to create an advertisement for the distributed corporate network of the CISCO company. To stimulate the students' imagination, the teacher conducts a brainstorming session based on previously prepared cards illustrating various types of television advertising. The students' preferences are revealed, and they talk about their priorities and negative impressions of advertising [6]. When the teacher asks the students to create an advertisement for the CISCO company in pair work, the students successfully complete the task using their homework. The winner is determined by a "secret vote".

CONCLUSION

Vocabulary plays an important role in learning a foreign language, since in order to communicate fluently in a foreign language, students must know a sufficiently large number of words and, in addition, in what context to use these words. By conducting role-playing and lexical games in a foreign language lesson, the teacher has the opportunity to create various hypothetical professionally-oriented situations in which students must use language to communicate, exchange information and express their own opinions. Conducting games contributes not only to increasing the vocabulary of students, but also to the development of their creative abilities. Didactic games are an effective tool for teaching a foreign language: they help to create a favorable and friendly atmosphere in the classroom, where during the game, students actively use vocabulary and develop their speech skills. Using a game in a foreign language lesson also contributes to the creation of psychological readiness of students for verbal communication.

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